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The United Nations Security Council And Management Of International Conflicts: The Case Of Syria

Wabara Meleen Ben Umor & Matthew Ogali

Faculty of Social Sciences
Department of Political & Administrative Studies
University Of Port Harcourt, Port Harcourt, Nigeria

ABSTRACT

The paper examined the role of the United Nations Security Council in the Management of International Conflicts using the Syrian conflict as a case study. The Methodology of the study involved descriptive research and qualitative data process. Data were obtained and analyzed from various secondary sources, such as journals, textbooks, online media reports. It was observed that the Syrian conflict has become a typical test case before the United Nations Security Council, whose responsibility it is to maintain international peace and security in terms of conflict prevention or prompt resolution based on the enormous powers that the Charter has bestowed on the Security Council. The study found that not only has the Security Council been ineffective and unable to perform its role in the management of international peace and security, the permanent members of the council are seemingly not passionate and committed to peace and security. It was clearly observed that the Security Council is bedeviled and enmeshed in internal crisis and challenges which have prevented the body from effectively discharging its functions for the good of the international community. Such problems were found to include: the deep-rooted animosity, division and rivalry among member-States of the Security Council which make them not to see things in the same direction. The paper concluded that the Security Council at its present state cannot effectively maintain international peace and security which are the fundamental objectives of its creation. The study recommended that since veto holding States have frequently abused their veto rights for their selfish national goals rather than the actual resolution of international conflicts, nations should insist on reforms of the security council, and on veto rights, to give more powers to the General Assembly to make more binding decisions, especially on matters of international peace, security and humanitarianism.

Keywords: The United Nations, Security Council, International Conflicts, International Peace, Security management

INTRODUCTION

The United Nations and the United Nations Security Council were created based on the earnest desire to prevent wars, destructions and humanitarian catastrophes in the world. It was hoped that nations would explore the peaceful processes offered by the UN to resolve international disputes without resorting to wars and bloodshed. It was also hoped that the UNSC would always unite and have a collective goal towards the management of international conflicts. However, these lofty expectations have not come to

light. The international system is still riddled and pervaded by wars, bloodshed and humanitarian catastrophes, while the UNSC seemingly stand aloof. The Syrian conflict is a typical example of raging conflicts in the world that the UNSC has been unable to effectively resolve.

The Syrian conflict has lasted more than both the first and second world wars, claiming the lives of over 500,000 and wounding over two million, Marauhn (2012). The problems facing the UNSC and by extension the United Nations include: entrenched division and rivalry among the permanent members of the council which have paralyzed the decision-making processes and the effectiveness of the council, lopsided representation in the council by which big powers such as Germany, Japan, India and Nigeria have been denied permanent membership of the council and as a result, the world is being denied of their enormous contributions to world peace and security, veto politics among the veto wielding members of the Security Council, by which veto is used apparently to protect and advance selfish national interests than international peace. Syria was purposively selected as a typical case that demonstrates the inability of the UNSC to unite and resolve international conflicts. For instance, between 2011 and 2024, Russia was found to have vetoed about seventeen UNSC's resolutions on Syria which would have seen the UN taken more powerful decisions on the conflict.

Theoretical Framework

Classical Realist Theory

The Classical realist theory apparently proposes the best explanations on the behaviours of States in the anarchical international system and the necessity for the use of force in a collective security approach in the management of international conflicts. Of utmost relevance to this study is the centrality of Power in its analysis of causes and effects. Power is the greatest source of contentions between States and non-states actors in the international system.

Proponents include: Thomas Hobbes, Thucydides, Hans Morgenthau, etc., but in this study particular reference is made on Thomas Hobbes' ideas on the state of nature. Hobbes postulated on the anarchy that exists in societies where there is absence of law and order or centralized authority in the Leviathan (1651). The actions or behaviours of States (and some non-state actors) accordingly, are likened to humans in the state of nature, full of greed and contentions which result in frequent strife and bloodshed. The UNSC was created to be a pseudo world government, to create maximum impetus for a lawful and peaceful international system. The implication of this theory is that the might of the Security Council is needed for the enforcement of world peace and security. The United Nations collective security system was built on the assumption that the Security Council will always be united to bring peace to the troubled world. The UNSC was expected to foster negotiations between States, impose sanctions on recalcitrant States or authorize the use of force in some cases to resolve international conflicts, especially when diplomacy has failed like the case of Syria.

Figure 1: Map of Syria, showing its territorial borders and central location as a West Asian country

METHODOLOGY

The study depended on secondary data sources from books, journals, newspapers, articles and online sources for information used for discussion and analysis. The research is basically qualitative, with a descriptive method of analysis, from which inferences for summary and conclusion were generated.

The UN Security Council (UNSC)

The UN Security Council is one of the principal organs of the United Nations (UN). It was inaugurated formerly on the 17th of January 1946 as a form of executive to the UN collective security system. The council consists of 15 members, of which 5 of them (the US, Great Britain, France, China and Russia) are veto wielding permanent member States, while the rest have non-permanent member statuses. Chapter VII of the UN charter explicitly outlines the roles and responsibilities of the Security Council. These basically include:

- to maintain international peace and security
- to develop friendly relations among nations
- to cooperate in solving international problems and in promoting respect for human rights
- and to be a centre for harmonizing the actions of nations.

Lesia and Ivasechko (2018), writing on the UN Security Council's veto rights reforms in the context of the conflict in Ukraine, observed that the activities of the United Nations Security Council have traditionally been seen as a guarantor of international peace and security with authority to discourage or end disturbances to international peace and security. Fernanda et'al (2021) notes that the UN Security

Council's operation is intrinsic to its formation, functioning under an exclusivist and hierarchical dynamic without the international community, with guidelines to its meetings and discussions held under biased perspectives. The UN organization and its principal organs and affiliated agencies have been striving since the beginning of the 21st century to address the unimaginable humanitarian crisis, civil wars and unprecedented refugee crisis ravaging many regions of the world, and has as a matter of facts, recorded a number of successes, Hiscock & Richards (1974). Nevertheless, it has remained largely unable to fulfill its mandate of preventing international conflicts which is the cardinal objective of its establishment, as exemplified by its inability to end the wars in Syria, Sudan, Ukraine, among others.

According to Hiscock & Richards, (1974), the challenges facing the UNSC and by extension the United Nations include: entrenched division and rivalry among member-states of the Security Council, veto politics among the big powers and permanent members of the UNSC, the problem of lopsided membership or inadequate representation in the council by which big powers such as Germany, Japan and India have been denied permanent membership of the Security Council and thus their enormous potential contributions to international peace and security denied

Management of International Conflict

As a concept, 'management' broadly relates to the use of limited resources combined with forecasting, planning, leadership and execution skills to achieve predetermined specific goals, (Ramcharan,1991). In other words, the concept of management resonates with the idea of skillfully using limited resources, together with good planning and leadership to achieve some predetermined goals. In this way, conflict management would mean the use of limited resources, together with good planning and leadership to bring peace to warring groups. This is because the goal of conflict management is to reduce the intensity of conflict and gradually return to peace. Furthermore, while writing on conflict management, Rahim (2002) in Ifunanya (2014, p.56), posits that:

Conflict management is the process of limiting the negative aspects of conflicts. The aim of conflict management is to enhance learning and group outcomes properly managed conflict can improve group outcome.

In the same vein, Vincent (1974) and Nte (2018), see conflict management as the same thing as conflict resolution. He described conflict Management Methods as the same as Conflict Resolution Mechanisms, (CRM). He defines conflict resolution mechanisms as the processes or methods for curbing a conflict and restoring peace. He stated that there are diverse methods of managing conflicts with varying degrees of formality, ranging from Formal Institutionalized Mechanisms, (FIM), to Alternative Disputes Resolution Mechanisms, (ADR). Formal institutionalized mechanisms include arbitration and adjudication; alternative dispute resolution mechanisms include mediation, negotiation, facilitation and conciliation. Again, writing on the concept of conflict management, Albert, et'al (2000) and (Church & Marks, (2001) in Okwu, (2015) argued that Conflict management in principle presupposes that all conflicts cannot be necessarily resolved, "but learning how to manage conflicts can decrease the odds of non-productive escalation" (p.45). They asserted that Conflict management involves acquiring skills related to conflict communication skills, and establishing a structure for management of conflict in a given environment.

The UN Security Council and Management of International Conflict

As noted previously in the study, the United Nations (UN) was born as a response to the persistent problems of international conflicts. Consequently, the whole structure of the United Nations was designed for the purposes of managing or mitigating various types of international problems, (Okwu, 2015). In 1992 the UN Secretary-General at the time Boutros Boutros-Ghali initiated an ambitious role for the UN in post-cold war through a seminal report titled "An Agenda for Peace" the report suggested different approaches for the UN in maintaining international conflicts. These roles have since been incorporated into the activities of the United Nations in its efforts to manage international peace and security. These roles as Lamy et'al (2014) helpfully highlighted, included: (1) Preventive Diplomacy, which involves confidence-building measures, fact finding, and preventive deployment of UN authorized force (2) Peace-

Making, designed to bring warring groups to a round table agreement (3) Peace-Keeping, which is the deployment of a UN presence in the field with the approval of all groups (4) Post-Conflict peace building, which is basically intended to develop the social, political and economic infrastructure of the area and prevent a relapse to the violence, and (5) Peace-Enforcement.

Lamy, et'al (2014) and Nte (2018), opined that there are eight major preventive diplomacy techniques which the United Nations and other intergovernmental organizations deploy to peacefully resolve conflicts, these include: (1) negotiation (2) mediation (3) facilitation (4) arbitration (5) adjudication (6) conciliation (7) fact finding (8) ombudsman mission. These techniques shall be briefly discussed below.

Negotiation: this happens when the warring factions or adversaries are involved in discussing the major contentious issues and willing participate in a bargaining process to lower tension and reach a settlement which should restore lasting peace. However, for negotiation to succeed as conflict resolution mechanism, parties must be willing to reach a compromise on salient issues. The UN negotiators weigh the possibility and constraints of negotiation in a conflict and make efforts to arrive at a win-win situation for all. Mediation: in mediation, a neutral party acceptable to the warring factions oversees the discussions that would enable the contending parties to arrive at a peaceful settlement.

The Syrian Conflict

The Syrian conflict began in 2011 when some angry traders in Hariqa Market in old Damascus embarked on a protest against human rights restrictions, and inhuman brutality by the Syrian regime through its security forces. The protests grew in rigour and protesters carried placards and shouted with the slogan “do not humiliate the Syrian people” according to Sini, et'al (2014) and Aljazeera (2023). From then on the protesters kept increasing and the protests spread to other cities and took a different dimension. a month later, hundreds or thousands of people, mostly young men and students gathered in the southern city of Daraa to protest against mounting poverty and injustices in the country, and demanding many things, including the sacking of the governor of the city, justice and peoples freedoms. When the protests overwhelmed Daraa and spread to other cities such as Homs and Aleppo, the central government became worried.

According to Kareem (2020), what happened was that the protests were spearheaded or well received by the Sunni Arab majority who made up about 65% of the total Syrian population; however, later on, protesters and demonstrators came from all over and across the country's diverse ethnic and religious communities. The government of Al Assad responded to these protests with extreme force, ordering maximum police and military action against the demonstrators, there was massive deployment of military units across Syrian cities with the mission of repressing the uprising.

The ensuing struggle between government forces and the protesters/demonstrators instantly resulted in casualties. The death and injuries of many protesters angered the demonstrators the more as well as the entire population. The maximum repression of the initially peaceful and unarmed protesters attracted immense international condemnation. Consequently, there was division among the country's population as well as the military, with some of the citizens and army supporting the government of Al Assad, while the others opposing al Assad and demanding his immediate resignation. The situation became worst just a few months later. The repression by government forces became deadlier with so many Syrians losing their lives; nevertheless, the opposition and protests grew in strength. The culmination of the protests and demonstrations was the formation of the Free Syrian Army (FSA), in 2012 which quickly attracted support from the west, particularly the United States, (Sini, et'al. 2022 and Kareem, 2020). By the end of 2023, the conflict would have lasted for a decade and two years; longer than the First and Second World Wars. There seems to be no accurate account of casualties. HelpAge, (2014) puts the figure as hundreds to thousands deaths and over six million displaced, generating the largest refugee crisis in the world, second only to the Rwandan genocide. Consequently, Clark, et'al (2015)

Almost half of the population of the country has been forced to leave their homes and seek refuge in neighbouring countries amounting to 3.2

million people among which are 1.7 million children. The conflict has also destroyed the country's economy, thus increasing poverty and inequality, (Clark, et'al, 2015.P.11).

The effect of the conflict has been much more devastating in the economy. According to the Syrian Centre for policy research, (SCPR), Syria has lost roughly 202 billion US dollars because of the lingering conflict, equivalent to 383% of the GDP of 2010, making the country dependent on foreign support. The group observed that the conflict has crashed Syria's Human Development Index, with more than 50% of the people now living in deprivation. it stated that about 12.6 million are currently living in poverty, while 4.4 million Syrians live in abject poverty.

Table 1: Shows some UNSC's Resolutions and Voting Pattern on the Syrian Conflict between 2012 and 2023.

RESOLUTION	DATE	VOTING	RESOLUTION OBJECT
S/RES/612	4 October 2011	*Vetoed by Russia	Condemning Syrian government's actions in Syria.
S/RES/77	4 April 2012	*Vetoed by Russia	Resolution to condemn the Syrian war
S/RES/2042	14 April, 2012	Unanimous Vote	Resolution on Humanitarian Situation
S/RES/2043	21 April 2012	Unanimous Vote	Resolution on the Establishment of a UN Monitoring Team (UNSMIS) in Syria.
S/RES/538	10 July 2012	*Vetoed by Russia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Seeking to activate Responsibility to Protect. • Resolution on Renewal of Mandate on Surveillance Mission in Syria.
S/RES/2059	20 July 2012	Unanimous Vote	
S/RES/2118	27 September 2013	Unanimous Vote	Resolution on the Elimination of the use of Chemical Weapons in Syria.
S/RES/2139	22 February 2014	Unanimous Vote	Resolution on Providing Access to Humanitarian Assistance in Syria.
S/RES/2165	14 July, 2014	Unanimous Vote	Resolution on Monitoring the Humanitarian Situation in Syria.
S/RES/2209	March 6, 2015	14-0-1(abstain: Venezuela)	Resolution on the Use of Chemical Weapons in Syria.
S/RES/2254	18 December, 2015	Unanimous Vote	Ceasefire Resolution
S/RES/2268	26 February, 2016	Unanimous Vote	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Resolution Regarding Political Negotiations between the Parties in Disputes. • Seeking to refer President al Assad and top military officers to the International Criminal Court.
S/RES/842	22 May 2016	*Vetoed by Russia	
S/RES/846	8 October 2016	*Vetoed by Russia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Seeking a ban on military flights over Aleppo and other cities. • Resolution on the OPCW's Mandate to identify the use of Chemical Weapons in Syria.
S/RES/2319	31 October 2016	Unanimous vote	
S/RES/2319	31 October, 2016	Unanimous vote	Resolution on the Renewal of the OPCW Mandate in Syria for a Year
S/RES/1026	5 December 2016	*Vetoed by Russia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Calling on Syrian Government to

S/RES/2328	19 December, 2016	Unanimous vote	Obey International Laws and Obligations <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Resolution on Granting Access to Civil Evacuation Monitoring Team from Aleppo.
S/RES/2332	21 December, 2016	Unanimous vote	Resolution on Authorizing Cross-Border Aid Shipments in Syria.
S/RES/172	28 February, 2017	*Vetoed by Russia and China	Resolution Seeking Extended Sanctions on Syrian Government.
S/RES/315	12 April 2017	*Vetoed by Russia	Resolution seeking military intervention in Syria.
S/RES/887	24 October	*Vetoed by Russia	Resolution Condemning Syria.
S/RES/962	16 November 2017	*Vetoed by Russia	Resolution calling on Syria to Respect International Laws.
S/RES/970	17 November 2017	*Vetoed by Russia	Resolution Alleging War crimes on Syria.
S/RES/321	10 April 2018	*Vetoed by China and Russia	Condemning Syria on the Humanitarian Catastrophes in Syria.
S/RES/756	19 September 2019	*Vetoed by China and Russia.	Resolution on Alleged War Crimes on the Syrian Authorities.
S/RES/961	20 December 2019	*Vetoed by China and Russia	Resolution to Initiate Responsibility to Protect (R2P).
S/RES/654	7 July 2020	*Vetoed by China and Russia	Resolution seeking military intervention
S/RES/667	10 July 2020	*Vetoed by China and Russia	Resolution calling on all Parties to Obey International/Humanitarian Laws in the War.
S/RES/2672	9 January 2024	*Vetoed by Russia	Resolution Seeking to Extend the Authorization for the Syrian Cross-Border aid Mechanism for Additional Six Months Until 10 July 2024.

Source: the Table was personally made but most Data from Kasanusi, et'al, (2022), and other online sources.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

As clearly seen from the above table, as many as seventeen (17) resolutions of the Security Council bearing asterisks in the table above, have been vetoed by Russia and China, revealing the entrenched division and factionalism within Security Council. A number of observations were also made in the study as highlighted and discussed below.

The Ineffectiveness of UNSC is due to the Conflicting roles Played by Different groups and Foreign Nations, including Russia, China, Iran, Turkey and the West.

Different groups have different interests and fought for their interests in the Syrian conflict. However, what is significantly common in the conflict is the conflicting and aggravating roles played by foreign nations in the conflict. Countries such as Russia, China, Iran and the West, particularly the United States, Great Britain and France played different roles in the conflict. The world super powers, with entrenched animosity against one another but afraid of the risk of directly fighting themselves, chose to fight through their proxies. Thus, the unilateral involvement, participation and interferences in domestic conflicts by foreign nations like the aforementioned have worsened the conflict. It was also noted earlier by Johan &

Duursma (2018), that the Syrian conflict is nothing other than “a free for all conflict” because of the different groups fighting for different interests and controlling different parts or territories of the countries. Baharul & Khan (2022) and Victoria (2023) have argued that a number of conflicts in the third world, particularly the Syrian war, were actually proxy wars, because they are obviously foreign powers such as the United States, Russia, the UK, France and Iran were battling for their economic, geopolitical and strategic interests through their respective proxies in Syria.

The UNSC has made Conflicting or Divergent Decisions on the Syrian and Sudan Conflicts which are Responsible for the Escalating Violence and Humanitarian Crises.

The table on pages 13-15 shows that up to 17 decisions of Security Council was vetoed by Russia and China. In its present state, the UNSC is incapable of making unified decisions on international peace and security due to the extreme factionalism in the council. The division, rivalry and factionalism in the council has created the scenarios or impression that the different factions often make divergent and conflicting decisions which only help in escalating the conflicts and violence in the international system as well as the humanitarian crises. Articles 24 & 42, expressly permits the UNSC to authorize the use of military force to restore peace and security whenever and wherever they are threatened in the international system. The expectations of the framers of the UN charter on the Security Council were lofty; several provisions were made in the charter that empowered the UNSC to work. According to article 39 of the UN charter as captured in Okwu (2015.p.67):

The security council shall determine the existence of any threat to peace, breach of peace, or any act of aggression and shall make recommendations, or decide what measures shall be taken in accordance with articles 41& 42, to maintain or restore international peace.

SUMMARY/CONCLUSION

The paper investigated the UN Security Council and the management of the Syrian conflict. We highlighted some of the efforts made by the Security Council, in terms of decisions and resolutions initiated by the body and particularly, the factors that have impinged on their effectiveness, like veto politics. We saw that out of over twenty five resolutions initiated by the Security Council for the purpose of direction intervention in the Syrian conflict, which would have probably the ended the war, seventeen of these were vetoed by Russia, at times alongside China. In this way, the Security Council has been largely paralyzed and incapable of ending conflict. In addition, the study yielded a number of findings which were discussed on pages 14-15 above. It can be stated that the United Nations Security Council’s approach to management of international conflicts in the 21st century has been found to be ineffective, its efforts in managing the Syrian conflict has been defective and unsuccessful due to the internal problems within the Security Council itself. Therefore, the United Nations Security Council in its present state cannot effectively maintain international peace and security. We recommend that since veto holding States have frequently abused their veto rights for their selfish national goals rather than the actual resolution of international conflicts, nations should insist on reforms of the security council, particularly the veto rights principle, to give more powers to the General Assembly to make more binding decisions, especially on matters of international peace, security and humanitarianism. This might be an extremely difficult task to engage in, because the five veto holding, permanent members of the Security Council have dismissed every effort or call for reformation of the Security Council and the veto rights principle, but the world must not give up trying.

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